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Effects Of Demonstration And Collaboration Method Of Teaching On Students' Achievement In Basic Technology In Secondary School In Delta State

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study was to investigate the impact of teaching approaches that prioritise collaboration and demonstration on students' academic performance in basic technology. The research was conducted in Delta State, Nigeria, adopting a pre-test, post-test, control group design, and a quasi-experimental methodology. The research population consisted of 140,959 Upper Basic 3 students from 475 Public Upper Basic Schools located in Delta State's 25 Local Government Areas. A total of 383 upper basic school pupils from three distinct schools were included in the sample. The study utilised a modified Basic Technology Test (BTT) that has been endorsed by Delta State's Examination and Standard Board for the 2020 examination year and validated by three experts. Statistical analyses, including mean, standard deviation, and two-way Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA), were used to evaluate the research questions and associated hypotheses about academic achievement scores among students taught using demonstration, collaboration, and lecture methods. An analysis of the data yielded the following conclusions: there was a notable disparity in the average academic achievement scores of secondary school students who were taught Basic Technology using demonstration, collaboration, and lecture methods. The preference for demonstration and collaboration methods over the lecture method was observed. Additionally, there was a significant interaction effect between the demonstration, collaboration, and lecture methods, and sex on students' academic achievement in Basic Technology. The study provides helpful details regarding basic technology teaching methods, emphasising the need for educators to employ cutting-edge teaching methods that cater to a range of students' requirements and raise academic achievement. The study recommended, among other things, that educators employ the very successful teaching method of cooperation and demonstration.

Keywords: Demonstration Method, Collaboration Method, Lecture Method, Academic Achievement

INTRODUCTION

The revised curriculum in Nigeria has established three distinct divisions for Basic Education: Lower Basic, encompassing Basic 1 to 3; Middle Basic, encompassing Basic 4 to 6; and Upper Basic, encompassing Junior Secondary 1 to 3. The country's Basic Education curriculum concludes with the Level of Upper Basic Education. In alternative terms, persons who successfully attain this level of education are regarded as having successfully completed Basic Education in Nigeria. The National Policy on Education (FGN, 2014) outlines the objectives of Upper Basic Education as fostering an enthusiasm for science and technology, obtaining essential knowledge and skills in these domains, using their knowledge and skills to address society demands, capitalising on the numerous career prospects in science and technology, and preparing for advanced studies in these areas.

Several elective courses are offered at the Upper Basic Education level to fulfil the stated objectives. One of these subjects is basic technology, which was established as a fundamental course to familiarise pupils with science and prepare them for more advanced science and technology education.

The study course is structured to facilitate students' understanding of the fundamental principles of science, the established methods for solving scientific issues, and the functions and objectives of science in everyday life and the broader society. Agbo, as cited in Sambo, Kukwi, Eggari & Mahmuda (2014), asserts that fundamental technology serves as the cornerstone of advanced science, technology, and engineering education. Upon the allocation and distribution of the UBE fund to the Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC) in July 2006, the implementation of the basic technology program commenced. The main objectives of this program are to equip students with the necessary laboratory and field skills, to impart them with relevant and relevant knowledge in the fundamental sciences, and to empower them to apply scientific knowledge to real-life experiences related to agriculture, personal and community health, and rational and practical scientific attitudes.

The three fundamental components of education—the teacher, the learner, and the core content—are essential for attaining the aforementioned objectives. It is the duty of teachers to instruct students in the subject matter, with the expectation that they will pay attention and understand it. Teachers have implemented several teaching methods to enhance students' performance in basic technology. These strategies range from learner-centred approaches to teacher-centered procedures. The most popular teaching approach in this region of the world appears to be the traditional lecture method, commonly known as teacher-centered whole-class teaching. With this method, the students must sit quietly and pay attention to the teacher as he explains the lesson's material. They must also provide answers to the teacher's queries and ask only a few questions when needed.

Another name for the traditional lecture format is "talk and chalk." This approach places a strong emphasis on the teacher, suggesting that the students are only passive recipients of the teacher's instruction. When using this method, the students don't participate very much in the lesson; instead, the teacher takes charge. Within this particular framework, the teacher is considered the ultimate source of all knowledge, while the students serve as the passive channels via which the instructors transmit the taught information. Upon the class's end, the student may have a few initial enquiries, or they may be required to answer a set of questions, offer comments, or document their progress.

One benefit of using the standard method is that it covers a wider area faster. It does, however, have a few drawbacks. It is typified, for instance, by a lack of student engagement to instructional materials, an emphasis on instructor behaviour rather than student behaviour, and a delay in providing feedback on students' performance. In essence, the approach to teaching fundamental technology is thought to be out of date; it places a significant load on students' learning that has minimal bearing on its advancement. This approach, according to Ughamadu (2006), is a blatant denial of the widely held belief that learning is an active process as opposed to a passive one. By identifying the persistent use of the lecture technique as a primary deficiency affecting higher education and achievement in the humanities, Olojobou (2009) confirmed the limitations of this approach. It is also vital to promote the adoption of alternative suitable teaching and learning strategies for basic technology in light of these shortcomings. When teaching basic technology, a variety of instructional strategies can be used. The researcher is intrigued by the application of collaboration and demonstration methods, nevertheless.

One way to characterise the demonstration teaching approach is as an exhibition or show that is typically carried out by the teacher while the pupils observe with great interest. Demonstration teaching can also be defined as an approach in which the instructor walks students through the tasks they will be expected to do at the end of the class, explaining each step along the way. Compared to other teaching strategies like the lecture approach, this one has a few advantages. In accordance with the findings of Ochogba et al. (2019), the demonstration teaching approach offers several advantages. Firstly, it saves time and promotes material economy. Secondly, it serves as an attention-grabbing and powerful motivator during lesson delivery. Thirdly, students receive immediate feedback through their own products. Fourthly, it provides a realistic scenario of the course of study, allowing students to acquire skills in real-life situations using tools and materials. Lastly, when implemented by competent teachers, it effectively motivates students and effectively demonstrates appropriate behaviour. Following an analysis of the advantages of the demonstration approach and its correlation with the teaching of fundamental technology, it is imperative to undertake research to ascertain the potential enhancement of students' academic performance in Basic Technology at Delta State. The study also examined the collaboration method as a teaching method.

A collaboration teaching method involves four or more students working together in person in a classroom to accomplish a shared objective of learning from a specific assignment. Peer collaboration

has generally been proposed by several scholars (Zimmerman, 2008; Destiny & Samuelson, 2010) as a more successful way to teach science to junior secondary school students. In the last decade, some educational experts have particularly supported this approach because of its advantageous impact on traditional classroom learning, which has been well evaluated in the academic achievements of students participating in remote education programs (Eggon & Agu, 2020). According to Poellhuber, Chiominne, and Karseti (2008), teaching science as self-regulated learning strategies and collaborative learning is one strategy to help students learn and understand science and the scientific method. Students that are taught collaboratively typically perform better academically, have stronger critical thinking abilities, and comprehend the content better (Ishaq, 2021). The current study aims to investigate the impact of collaborative teaching methods on students' academic progress in basic technology, taking into account the benefits that have been seen. Male and female students will use the two teaching strategies to see if there is any potential for gender interaction in the application of the methods.

The gender question is relevant in science education today, especially in light of the growing focus on measures to increase the number of women working in science and technology as well as the number of men needed for technological advancement. Gender bias remains pervasive in Nigeria and possibly throughout Africa. In Africa, especially in Nigeria where gender inequalities are highlighted, sex roles are somewhat rigid. Gender stereotypes are frequently observed in the daily lives of Nigerians, as certain occupations such as medical, engineering, and architecture have historically been associated with men, while other professions such as nursing, catering, typing, and the arts have generally been associated with women. Generally speaking, girls are assigned to do household chores like dishwashing, cooking, cleaning, and so on, whereas boys are called upon to wash vehicles, mow the lawn, change lightbulbs, or climb ladders to fix or remove objects. Simply said, ladies are anticipated to engage in the relatively simple and less challenging tasks, while boys are allocated the intricate and arduous ones. This kind of thinking led to the general public's perception of girls as the "weaker sex." As such, the typical Nigerian youngster carries these established stereotypes with them to school. But according to Erinosh (quoted in Ishaq, 2021), gender concerns have been shown to have an overall negative impact on achievement, both for students and teachers. Given this, it is necessary to determine whether teaching methods such as collaborative and demonstration differ significantly between male and female basic technology students.

Statement of the Problem

According to reports from multiple states in Nigeria, students do poorly in junior secondary school examinations especially in basic technology. Because of their subpar performance, many basic technology students, according to Ekefre in Abdullahi (2016), are unable to understand simple machine designs. According to Ogide (2017), some teachers' use of the lecture method is to blame for students' subpar performance in basic technology classes. Teachers in schools primarily employ the teacher-centered lecture method, which implies that students are passive and that learning is typically surface-level. Thus, the low academic achievement of students in basic technology may be attributed to some basic technology teachers' use of this method.

Basic technology is a practical discipline that encompasses the study of electrical electronics, mechanical engineering, woodworking, construction, automobile engineering, and technical drawing. Therefore, the instruction of fundamental technology will require a student-centered methodology in which students are actively engaged in classroom instruction. Instead of exclusively depending on the conventional approach, such as the lecture method, it is imperative to adopt activity-stimulating and student-centered techniques, such as collaborative and demonstrative methods, in order to enhance student achievement. In this sense, the study's main question is: How much will students' academic achievement in basic technology increase if demonstration and collaborative teaching methods are used?

Purpose of the Study

This study set out to find out how students' achievement in basic technology was affected by teaching methods that emphasise collaboration and demonstration. In particular, the research sorts to:

1. Examine the variations in the average academic achievement scores of secondary school students who were taught basic technology through demonstration method (DM), collaboration method (CM) and lecture method (LM).

2. discover how students' academic achievement in basic technology is affected by the interaction between the DM, CM, LM, and sex.

Research Questions

To direct the investigation, one research question was posed:

1. What is the difference in the average academic achievement scores of students in Delta State's secondary schools who were taught basic technology through the DM, CM and LM?

Hypotheses

1. The mean academic achievement scores of secondary school pupils in Delta State who were taught basic technology through DM, CM and LM did not differ significantly.
2. The academic achievement of Delta State basic technology students is not significantly affected by the combination of DM, CM, LM and sex.

RESEARCH METHOD

The study employed a quasi-experimental research design. The current study's quasi-experimental research methodology, which employed intact classes and non-randomization, is considered the most appropriate. Three groups—two experimental and one control—were used in the investigation. One of the experimental groups received instruction via the demonstration teaching method, the other experimental group received instruction using the collaborative teaching method, and the control group received no instruction at all. 140,959 Upper Basic 3 pupils from 475 Public Upper Basic Schools made up the study's population. 383 Delta State students made up the study's sample. They were chosen from three schools in each of the state's three senatorial districts. The selection of the schools was done by simple random sampling. The study employed an adapted version of the Basic Technology Test (BTT), which was created and approved by Delta State Exams and Standards to be used in the 2020 exam year. There were sixty multiple-choice questions in the exam. Three specialists in the Department of Technical Education, one of whom was the supervisor of the researcher, assessed the face and content validity of the BTT. It was expected of the experts to ascertain whether the instrument's face and content validity was appropriate and pertinent to the study's purpose. Before the final draft was created, the experts' various comments were taken into consideration and included into the instrument. The BTT was pilot-tested on a sample of thirty Edo State basic technology students in order to evaluate the test's reliability. Kuder Richardson 20 (KR20), which yields an internal consistency metric, was used to examine the data. A 0.84 coefficient was found. Before the treatment, the researcher gave the test to every student in the experimental and control groups with the assistance of six research assistants. The initial group equivalency of the students was ascertained using the results of the pre-test. Students in the three groups took a post-test following the six-week treatment period in order to assess the treatment's effectiveness. The acquired data were analysed with Two-way ANCOVA, mean, and standard deviation.

RESULTS

- *What is the difference in the average academic achievement scores of students in Delta State's secondary schools who were taught basic technology through the DM, CM and LM?*

Table 2: Variations in the average academic achievement scores of secondary school students who were taught basic technology by DM, CM and LM.

Teaching Method	<i>n</i>	Mean	SD
DM	128	58.91	1.217
CM	128	58.63	.719
LM	127	43.54	5.234
Total	383	53.72	7.830

The average academic performance scores of secondary school students who were instructed in fundamental technology using cooperative, demonstration, and lecture approaches are compared in Table 2. The group implemented the demonstration teaching method achieved an average score of 58.91, with a standard deviation of 1.22. The group utilising the collaboration teaching method obtained

an average score of 58.63, with a standard deviation of 0.72. The group employing the lecture method achieved an average score of 43.54, with a standard deviation of 5.23. The results indicate that secondary school students who received instruction in Basic Technology via demonstration, collaboration, and lecture approaches produced different average academic achievement scores.

- The mean academic achievement scores of secondary school pupils in Delta State who were taught basic technology through DM, CM and LM did not differ significantly.

Table 3: ANOVA summary table comparing the mean academic achievement scores of secondary school students who were taught basic technology through DM, CM and LM.

ANOVA						
Post-Test						
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Between Groups	19715.720	2	9857.860	1010.957	.000	
Within Groups	3705.387	380	9.751			
Total	23421.107	382				
Multiple Comparisons						
Dependent Variable: Post-Test						
Tukey HSD						
(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Demonstration	Collaboration	.281	.390	.751	-.64	1.20
	Control	15.379*	.391	.000	14.46	16.30
Collaboration	Demonstration	-.281	.390	.751	-1.20	.64
	Control	15.097*	.391	.000	14.18	16.02
Control	Demonstration	-15.379*	.391	.000	-16.30	-14.46
	Collaboration	-15.097*	.391	.000	-16.02	-14.18

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 3 presents a one-way ANOVA that assesses the variations in the average academic achievement outcomes of secondary school students who received instruction in fundamental technology through DM, CM, and LM. The outcome indicates that p (0.000) is less than 0.05, and F = 1010.957. Based on the p-value being less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. These findings suggest a significant disparity in the mean academic performance scores among secondary school students who received instruction in fundamental technology using demonstration, collaboration, and lecture approaches. The results of the multiple comparison test indicate that students' accomplishment scores are significantly greater when they engage in collaboration and use demonstration techniques compared to the lecture method. Nevertheless, the average academic performance scores of pupils who received instruction through display and cooperation approaches are comparable.

- The academic achievement of Delta State basic technology students is not significantly affected by the combination of demonstration, collaboration and lecture method and sex.

Table 4: ANCOVA summary table demonstrating the interaction between sex and teaching method on students' achievement in basic technology

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects									
Dependent Variable: Post-Test									
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta		
Corrected Model	20722.558 ^a	6	3453.760	481.227	.000	.885			
Intercept	8783.412	1	8783.412	1223.829	.000	.765			
Pretest	1.208	1	1.208	.168	.682	.000			
Group	19771.442	2	9885.721	1377.418	.000	.880			
Sex	120.088	1	120.088	16.732	.000	.043			
Group * Sex	778.979	2	389.489	54.269	.000	.224			
Error	2698.549	376	7.177						
Total	1128723.000	383							
Corrected Total	23421.107	382							

Based on the data presented in Table 4, $F = 54.27$, $p(0.000) < 0.05$. Given that the p -value is below 0.05, it is imperative to reject the null hypothesis. This finding suggests a significant interaction impact between the instructional approach and gender on students' proficiency in fundamental technology.

DISCUSSION

According to one of the findings, secondary school students taught Basic Technology by lecture, demonstration, and cooperation methods had significantly different mean academic accomplishment scores. The results demonstrated that students in the group that used collaboration and demonstration outperformed those in the group that used the lecture method, suggesting that both approaches are useful for teaching and understanding basic technology. This finding aligns with the study conducted by Oniya and Adefila (2015), which investigated the impact of collaborative teaching on students' learning achievements in scientific practical skills at the elementary level in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Their findings revealed that the post-test performance of students in collaborative teaching groups was notably superior to that of the control group. It also concurs with Al-Rawi's (2013) findings, which indicate that the demonstration teaching approach is beneficial for imparting scientific laboratory experimentation and tool handling abilities. The results further support the findings of Sweeder and Jeffrey (2013), who demonstrate that demonstration methods have the potential to significantly contribute to students' development of a rich and deep understanding of the concepts taught in biology if they are carefully planned and integrated into the learning process.

The research findings also indicated a significant interaction effect among gender, teamwork, demonstration, and lecture approaches on students' academic performance in fundamental technology. The findings support the findings of Shamle and Ibrahim (2019), who investigated the impact of visual demonstration techniques on the academic performance of senior secondary school students in Geographic Information System (GIS). The researchers found that male students surpassed female students in Geographic Information Systems (GIS). However, this finding contradicts the results of Eggon and Agu (2020), who observed no statistically significant disparity in the average achievement scores of male and female students who were instructed in Basic Science and Technology using a peer-collaborative classroom method. The findings of this study are in direct opposition to the findings of Jirgba et al. (2018), who examined the impact of the peer collaboration teaching approach on the academic performance of Upper Basic 2 students in basic science in Makurdi Local Government Area, Benue State. An analysis revealed that there was no statistically significant disparity in the average achievement scores between male and female students who received instruction in fundamental science through the peer-collaborative learning approach. The present outcome also challenges the conclusions given by Adedayo (2014), who saw no noticeable difference in the performance between males and girls. Furthermore, the findings contradict the findings of Ayimbila and Pappoe (2021), who investigated the influence of the Demonstration-cum-Discussion teaching approach on the academic achievement of Navrongo Senior High School students in ecological concepts. The authors reported that there was no significant difference in the scores of male and female students in the experimental group on the pretest and posttest exercises.

CONCLUSION

The study's conclusions support the notion that collaboration and demonstration methods are equally successful methods for imparting basic technology knowledge. Compared to the traditional lecture method, which has been around for a long time, they are better. While both teaching methods are useful for teaching Basic Technology, the demonstration method seems to have greater promise for raising students' proficiency levels than the collaboration method.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The conclusions and findings led to the following recommendations being made:

1. Since demonstration and cooperation are more effective teaching methods than the lecture method, educators should implement them.
2. Periodically, government organisations or other pertinent organisations should provide teacher training on the use of collaboration and demonstration-based teaching methods.

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